

Electrical Engineering: An International Journal (EEIJ)

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Call for papers

Electrical Engineering: An International Journal (EEIJ) is a Quarterly peer-reviewed and refereed open access journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of Electrical Engineering. The journal is devoted to the publication of high quality papers on theoretical and practical aspects of Electrical Engineering.

The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on advancements, and establishing new collaborations in these areas. Original research papers, state-of-the-art reviews are invited for publication in all areas of Electrical Engineering.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to the following.

- Advanced Power System and Control system
- Analog and digital circuit design
- Applied Electromagnetics
- Artificial Intelligence and Artificial Life
- Bio Informatics
- Biomedical Instrumentation
- Communications and Networks
- Control, Intelligent Systems and Robotics
- Digital signal processing
- Embedded Systems and Robotics
- Hardware Formal Verification
- Information systems and network security
- Integrated Circuits and Embedded Systems
- Mechatronics and Avionics
- Microelectronic Technologies, Devices, CAD
- Microwave, Nano Devices and RF
- Non Conventional Energy Resources
- Optical Networks & communication
- Optimization techniques
- Photonics
- Power and Energy Systems
- Power Electronics & Electric Drives
- Remote sensing and satellite communication
- RF and Microwave Engineering
- Semiconductor Devices

- Sensor technology & Virtual Instrumentation
- Signal Processing and New Media
- Soft computing / Nano computing / Grid computing
- Software Engineering and Real-time Systems
- System Modeling & Simulation

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through **E-mail**: eeij@airccse.org. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : August 01, 2023**
- Notification : September 01, 2023
- Final Manuscript Due : September 08, 2023
- Publication Date: Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

For other details please visit <http://airccse.com/eeij/index.html>

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